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Application of Teak Leaves and Banana Trunk in Textile Industry for Dye removal: A Review

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ABSTRACT

In our India very fast-growing textile industries network uses huge quantity of potable water for the fibre production for various other purposes. Generally, it is calculated that nearly 200 liters of water is required for manufacturing 1 kg of textile material. Already we all know that the availability of water on earth and its value as far as scarcity is concerned. After manufacturing one kg of textile material if 200-liter water is in use and finally it is converted into wastewater. Water streams get polluted and available contaminants alter the water habitat and reduce biodiversity apart from changing the pH of water. It is our responsibility to think technically and to recover this polluted water and how it would be come in to use again for different purposes.

Keywords: *Textile, water, pollution, stream*

INTRODUCTION

As we know that due to increasing growth of population and industrialization also improvement in living standard there are so many industries coming in to existence to fulfil the demands of peoples regarding garments as per their living standards. Because the textile industry uses large quantities of dyes for numerous processes—the most common of which is silk methylene blue—the production of textiles has a significant impact on stream pollution. MB's chemical formula is $C_{16}H_{18}N_3SC$. First. According to a World Bank estimate, the textile industry is responsible for 17–20% of water contamination.[1]

It is very challenging task to treat the wastewater coming from textile industries. It requires major treatment for water receiving bodies due to the chemical composition and high concentration dye in wastewater. Dyes have synthetic origin and complex aromatic molecular structure. This structure makes it more difficult to biodegrade. [2] There are many ways technologies are available for dye removal such as physical, chemical and biological methods but they are so expensive and cause secondary pollution. [3,4]

Many methods and techniques have come into existence. Some researchers treat wastewater with the help of materials such as teak leaves and banana trunks with their own techniques and ways with same materials and concludes with good results.

EXAMPLES FROM LITERATURE REVIEW

Review Paper 1

D P Nagarajappa et. Al, (2023) studied the naturally and freely available materials like Teak leaves and Banana trunks are available in large amount. By treating textile effluents with chemicals is may costlier so by utilizing teak leaves and banana trunks as low-cost natural

adsorbent to treat the MB synthetic wastewater of concentration 10 mg/l. Take washed and collected material so unwanted impurities will be reduced. Then scorched below daylight for 1 week and converted it in to a power form with the help of mixer. activated with 80% orthophosphoric acid and 0.1 HNO_3 , respectively. In order to make an artificial solution, 1g of MB powder was diluted in 1L of de-mineralized water. The mixture was then maintained in a magnetic stirrer for 30 minutes to ensure uniform mixing before being diluted according to the experiment's specifications. Many factors, such as the adsorbent dosage, the pH of the solution, and the duration of contact between the adsorbent and the adsorbate, influence removal capacity. To determine the ideal dosage and pH, a jar test was carried out by varying the adsorbent dosage, pH, and contact time.[5]

Review Paper 2

S. Panneerselvam et. Al, (2022) studied in this case, prepare the activated adsorbent from teak leaves and banana trunk to remove the color from effluent, the column adsorption technique is adopted and evaluate the efficiency of the activated teak leaves and banana trunk in the removal of synthetic dye through batch experiments. Finally, the challenges and prospects of wastewater treatment are summarized. This study provides useful theoretical guidance for scientists in the fields of environmental science, environmental[7]

engineering, and environmental health. For that requirement, instruments are hot air oven, muffle furnace, magnetic stirrer, photometric calorimeter. Place the teak and banana trunks at $410^{\circ}C$ and $770^{\circ}C$ in muffle furnace at respective temperatures for next 40 min. and 90 min. respectively. In this way activated carbon produced from teak leaves and banana trunk can be effectively used for the dye removal from

industrial effluent. Compared to teak leaves, banana trunks are more efficient. In order for the 2:1 ratio of teak leaves to banana trunk to demonstrate greater color removal effectiveness. Thus the treated water is used for secondary uses such as construction, laundering, and flu.

Review Paper 3

Shristirupa Borah et. Al, (2024) studied that when we go through the plant based dyes in textile industries then they are act as ecofriendly nature. Using extracts from teak (*Tectona grandis*) leaves and metal mordants, an attempt is made to investigate the dyeing and functional finishing of mulberry silk. This technique improves the silk fabric's fastness qualities, color strength, antibacterial activity, and UV protection capacity. The best solvent system for extracting functional components from teak leaves was found to be methanol/water/HCl based on total polyphenols, flavonoids, and antioxidant activity. The methanol/water solvent solution with HCl at pH 2.5 (K/S = 48.338) and temperature at 80 °C (K/S = 28.009) for a 45-minute dyeing duration produced the maximum color yield. The silk dyed using a methanol/water/HCl solvent solution had the highest UPF values (UPF = 56.10), whereas the silk dyed with alum mordant showed good fastness properties (rating 4–5). When *Staphylococcus epidermis* MTCC435 was dyed with methanol/water and methanol/water/HCl solvent extracts using alum mordant, the silk fabric shown strong antibacterial activity. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to show the bonding interactions. The study showed that teak extracts are sustainable, plentiful, and safe coloring ingredients suitable for industrial mulberry silk dyeing.[8,9]

Review Paper 4

In this research, Shivanna S. et al. (2019) discuss two inexpensive, locally accessible

renewable bio-absorbents that are utilized to remove synthetic dye from aqueous solutions: banana trunks and teak leaves. Examined were the effects of dye concentration, bioabsorbent particle size, bioabsorbent amount, effective absorbance, and the applicability of Freudrich and Langmuir isotherms. Teak leaves were shown to be more bio-absorbent than banana trunks, absorbing 80% of the dye from a synthetic effluent at a particle size of 2 mm x 4 mm and 91% at 600 microns. In the instance of dye adsorption utilizing teak leaves, both of these additional methods were found to be appropriate. According to the author, the efficiency of banana trunk adsorbent is significantly higher than that of teak leaves. This is predicated on test parameter number two, which is the effective dosage test. For the same volume of the effluent sample (100 ml), 100 mg of adsorbent is needed for *Tectona grandis* and 50 mg for *Musa*. [10]

CONCLUSION

As per the detailed study of literature review here we can conclude that firstly above said material that is Teak leaves and Banana trunks is one of the best ecofriendly and easily available material with minimal cost and also uses of it by different way also can gives us a good results of removing dye molecules from waste water and also we can reuse the treated water for different purposes.

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